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1. Cameron Weishaar, 1–5
2. Kahlid Mankal, 6–9
3. Graham Jenkins, 10–13
4. Walter Salubro, 14–18
5. Kyle Longo, 19–21

1

Improvement in Trauma-Induced Neck, Back, and Shoulder Pain and Disability Following Correction of Sagittal and Coronal Spinal Alignment and Posture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report. [Oral Presentation at CBP® 44th Annual Convention, September 2-4, 2022, Nashville, TN, USA]

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case documenting the successful improvement of trauma-induced neck, back, and right shoulder pain and disability following the correction of sagittal and coronal spinal alignment and posture using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) spinal rehabilitation.

Clinical Features: A 57-year-old male presented to a chiropractic office with chief complaints of neck pain (NP) and low back pain (LBP) caused by lifting a water trough and right anterior shoulder pain caused by a fall from his bicycle. The patient rated his NP and LBP 2/10 on a visual analog scale (VAS) from 0 to 10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain. The patient rated his right anterior shoulder pain 5/10 on a VAS.

Pre-treatment physical examination revealed restricted cervical (extension and right rotation) and lumbar (extension, left and right lateral flexion, and left rotation), and right shoulder ranges of motion (ROM). Orthopedic testing elicited paresthesia of the right and left C6/C7 dermatome. Pre-treatment patient reported outcomes (PRO) included the Neck Bournemouth Questionnaire (NBQ) to assess the patient's self-reported NP and disability scoring 10% (on a scale of 0% to 100% where 0% is no disability and 100% is complete disability) and a Back Bournemouth Questionnaire (BBQ) to assess the patient's self-reported LBP and disability scoring 10%.

Pre-treatment posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Sagittal posture analysis revealed anterior translation of the pelvis (+TzP) and head (+TzH), posterior translation (-TzT) and forward flexion (+RxT) of the thorax (Figure 1A). Coronal posture analysis revealed right rotation of

the pelvis (-RyP) and thorax (-RyT), right thorax translation (-TxT), and left head translation (+TxH) (Figure 2A).

Pre-treatment radiographic examination and analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records (EHR) Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Sagittal radiographs revealed sagittal translation of C2 with respect to C7 (Tz C2-C7) measuring 30.8 mm (ideal is 0 mm), increased thoracic kyphosis (absolute rotational angle (ARA)) from T1 to T12 (ARA T1-T12) measuring 59.4° (ideal is 44°) (Figure 3A). Coronal radiographs revealed coronal translation of C2 with respect to S1 (Tx C2-S1) measuring -8.0 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 4A).

Interventions & Outcomes: The patient was prescribed a phase 1 care plan of 36 in-office visits over 12 weeks. The patient received CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments involving positioning the patient prone in -TzP, +RyP, +RyT, +TxT, +TzT, and -TzH with use of a drop table and administering Diversified, drop table, and IMPAC Pro-ArthroStim® Adjusting Instrument (I.M.P.A.C. Inc., Salem, OR, USA) adjustments (Figure 5). MI therapeutic exercises included +TzT and -TzH posturing on a whole body vibration (WBV) Power Plate® Pro (Power Plate Performance Health Systems, LLC, Northbrook, IL, USA) and +TzT and -TzH posturing against the wall (Figure 6). MI mechanical traction included +TzT, -TzP, and +TyT positioning on a Robo-Trac Decompression and Traction Unit (Advanced Spinal Rehab, Middletown, NY, USA) and +TzT and -TzH positioning using Universal Tractioning Systems (UTS) Total Spine Unit (Universal Tractioning Systems, Inc., Las Vegas, NV, USA) with the patient in a seated position (Figure 7).

The patient was prescribed at-home daily MI therapies to supplement in-office treatment. At-home MI exercises included using a CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser (Chiropractic BioPhysics®, Eagle, ID, USA) and -TzH, +TxT, and +TzT posturing. At-home MI mechanical traction included using a Thoracic Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) positioning the fulcrum at T8/T9 to create -RxT and a Lumbar Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic positioning the fulcrum at T12/L1 to create +TzT and -RxT. Ergonomic recommendations included using a Chiroflow® Professional Waterbase™ Pillow (Chiroflow®, Wheeling, IL, USA) for sleeping and a right heel lift measuring 9 mm to level the sacrum for healthy spinal foundation biomechanics. Nutrition recommendations included a multi-vitamin, anti-inflammatory diet and supplements, vitamin D3 and K2, and antispasmodic supplements.

Phase 1 post-treatment exam revealed improvements in the patient's NP at 0/10 on a VAS, LBP at 1/10 on a VAS, and his right anterior shoulder pain at 0/10 on a VAS. Phase 1 post-treatment NBQ scored 6% disability due to NP and BBQ scored 11% disability due to LBP. Phase 1 post-treatment posture analysis revealed +TzH (Figure 1B) and -RyP and -TxT (Figure 2B). Cervical extension was decreased, but all other orthopedic testing was within normal limits (WNL). First post-treatment exam was performed. Sagittal radiographs revealed improvement in Tz C2-C7 to 22.0 mm and ARA T1-T12 to 51.8° (Figure 3B). Coronal radiographs revealed increased Tx C2-S1 to -22.6 mm (Figure 4B) which became a prioritized focus in the second phase of corrective care.

The patient was prescribed a phase 2 care plan of 36 in-office visits over 12 weeks. The patient received CBP® MI adjustments involving positioning the patient prone in +RyP, +TxT, and -TzH with use of a drop table and administering Diversified, drop table, and Pro-ArthroStim® instrument adjustments (Figure 8). MI therapeutic exercises included +TxT posturing on a WBV Power Plate® with kettlebell work (Figure 9A) and +TxT posturing using the XZ Traction Wall Unit (Circular Traction Supply, Inc., Huntington Beach, CA, USA) (Figure 9B). MI mechanical traction included +TxT positioning on a 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) (Figure 10).

The patient was prescribed at-home daily MI therapies to supplement in-office treatment. At-home MI exercises included using a CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser and -TzH and +TxT posturing. At-home MI mechanical traction included reducing the frequency of the Thoracic and Lumbar Denneroll™ tractions. Ergonomic recommendations included continued use of the Chiroflow® Professional Waterbase™ Pillow (Chiroflow®, Wheeling, IL, USA) for sleeping and the right heel lift measuring 9 mm. Nutrition recommendations included continued use of a multi-vitamin, anti-inflammatory diet and supplements, vitamin D3 and K2, and antispasmodic supplements.

Phase 2 post-treatment exam revealed maintained or further improvements in the patient's NP at 0/10 on a VAS, LBP at 1/10 on a VAS, and his right anterior shoulder pain at 0/10 on a VAS. Phase 2 post-treatment NBQ scored 6% disability due to NP and BBQ scored 4% disability due to LBP. Phase 2 post-treatment posture analysis revealed +RxT (Figure 2C). Cervical ROM and all other orthopedic testing was WNL.

Phase 2 post-treatment exam was performed. Sagittal radiographs revealed maintained improvement in Tz C2-C7 to 22.0 and ARA T1-T12. Coronal radiographs revealed improvement in Tx C2-S1 to -3.3 mm (Figure 4C).

The patient was prescribed supportive at-home MI exercises and traction 1 to 2 times per week to supplement in-

office treatment. Ergonomic and nutrition recommendations were encouraged.

Conclusion: This case shows CBP® corrective MI adjustments, exercises, and tractions are an effective method to correct spinal alignment and posture which can result in improvement and long-term maintenance of neck, back, and shoulder pain and disability in adult populations. More high-quality research with long-term follow-ups are needed to further our understanding of this and better our strategies at helping patients.

Figure 1. A) Pre-Treatment, B) Post-Phase 1 Treatment, and C) Post-Phase 2 Treatment Sagittal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 2. A) Pre-Treatment, B) Post-Phase 1 Treatment, and C) Post-Phase 2 Treatment Coronal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal coronal posture. The red lines represent the actual coronal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 3. A) Pre-Treatment, and B) Post-Phase 1 Treatment Sagittal Full Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual C2-L6 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 5. Phase 1 Treatment CBP® Mirror Image® A) Sagittal, and B) Coronal Adjustment Setups

Figure 4. A) Pre-Treatment, B) Post-Phase 1 Treatment, and C) Post-Phase 2 Treatment 2 Coronal Full Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal spinal alignment. The red lines represent the actual C2-S1 coronal spinal alignment of the patient.

Figure 6. Phase 1 Treatment CBP® Mirror Image® Exercises on a Whole Body Vibration Power Plate®

Figure 7. Phase 1 Treatment CBP® Mirror Image® Traction A) Supine on Robo-Trac, and B) Seated in UTS Total Spine Unit

Figure 8. Phase 2 Treatment CBP® Mirror Image® A) Sagittal, and B) Coronal Adjustment Setups

Figure 9. Phase 2 Treatment CBP® Mirror Image® Exercises Using a A) Whole Body Vibration Power Plate®, and B) XZ Traction Wall Unit

Figure 10. Phase 2 Treatment CBP® Mirror Image® Traction using a 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System

2

Improvement in Thoracolumbar Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliosis Using ScoliBrace® Thoracolumbosacral Orthosis and Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report and Long-Term Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case demonstrating the successful reduction of adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS) of the thoracolumbar TL spine in a 13-year-old female using a ScoliBrace® Thoracolumbosacral Orthosis (TLSO) (ScoliCare®, Kogarah, New South Wales, Australia) and Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) structural spinal rehabilitation with a 1-year long-term follow-up

Clinical Features: A 13-year-old female presented to a chiropractic office with TL AIS after her mother was not satisfied with the posture outcomes using a Rigo-Cheneau (R-C) brace from the hospital. The patient reported 0/10 LBP on a numeric rating scale (NRS) of 0 to 10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain. Post-R-C/pre-ScoliBrace® posture analysis revealed large left coronal malposition of the thorax (+TxT), right lateral flexion of the thorax (+RzT), low left shoulder, and waist asymmetry (Figures 1A & 2A). Post-R-C/pre-ScoliBrace® radiography examination analysis confirmed a left TL AIS with a Cobb angle of measurement from T10 to L4 (apex at T12) (Cobb T10-L4 (T12)) measuring 36° (ideal is 0°). Radiographic findings included coronal translation of T12 with respect to S1 (Tx T12-S1) measuring 59 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and Tx T1-S1 measuring 43 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 3A). The patient was a Risser 0-, had a large sacral unleveling with a horizontal base angle (HBA) measuring -9.1° (ideal is 0) creating a low left sacrum measuring -27.4 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and had an anatomical leg length inequality (ALLI) measuring 9.3 mm short on the left leg (Figure 4). Post-R-C/pre-ScoliBrace® scoliometer measurement of the angle of trunk rotation (ATR) during Adam's forward bending test was -13° at T12.

Interventions and Outcomes: The patient was prescribed a ScoliBrace® TLSO in March 2020 for full-time wear (20-23 h/d) and monitored every 3 to 6 months for 2 years. The ScoliBrace® was able to support the patient in an over-corrected position creating a better position of the 3-dimensional posture of the body in order to retrain the brain, joints, and muscles to control the body posture to adapt to a new healthier normal (Figures 1B & 2B).

The patient began CBP® spinal rehabilitation in January 2022 involving Mirror Image® chiropractic adjustments, therapeutic exercises, and mechanical traction at a frequency of 1 treatment session per week for 6 months and then 2 treatment sessions per month for one year for a total of 45 treatment sessions over 14 months. The patient was also prescribed a 10 mm foot lift for her left foot to address the ALLI and sacral unleveling. MI therapies involve positioning the patient in a corrected or over-corrected postural position. MI adjustments involved positioning the patient in their opposite posture seated on a drop table and standing, involving -RzT, -TxT, and then TyT in that order, and applying adjustments with an Impulse® Adjusting Instrument (Neuromechanical Innovations, Chandler, AZ, USA) (Figure 5). MI therapeutic exercises included posturing in the -RzT, -TxT, and then +TyT position as well as lying left side down on a Thoracic ScoliRoll® Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) on the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) leveraging T12 to hold the spine in a corrected position while performing core strengthening movements like leg circles (Figure 6). MI mechanical traction was performed using the 3-D

Denneroll™ Traction Table System with the patient lying right side down and a strap pulling down into the left TL curve while another strap holds the pelvis neutral (Figure 7).

Post-ScoliBrace®/CBP® posture analysis revealed improvement in +TxT, +RzT, low left shoulder, and waist asymmetry. Post-ScoliBrace®/CBP® radiography examination analysis revealed improvement in in Cobb T10-L4 (T12) to 25°, Tx T12-S1 to 25 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and Tx T1-S1 to 9 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 3B).

Long-term follow-up posture analysis revealed improvement in +TxT, +RzT, low left shoulder, and waist asymmetry (Figures 1C & 2C). Long-term follow-up radiography examination analysis revealed continued improvement in Cobb T10-L4 (T12) to 25°, Tx T12-S1 to 20 mm (ideal is 0 mm), and Tx T1-S1 to 0 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 3C). Long-term follow-up scoliometer measurement of the ATR was -5° at T12.

Conclusions: In this case, where a Rigo-Cheneau brace was unsuccessful, ScoliBrace® TLSO and CBP® MI chiropractic adjustments, therapeutic exercises, and mechanical traction were a successful method to treat coronal spinal alignment in a 13-year-old female patient with TL AIS. Improvement in spinal alignment and posture may result in avoidance of spinal surgery. The patient and her mother stated that they were very happy with the improvements in spinal alignment and posture. More research is needed on this topic, in terms of case studies and long-term outcomes in the scoliosis population.

Figure 1A-C. Post-R-C/Pre-ScoliBrace® TLSO, In-ScoliBrace® TLSO, and 1-Year Follow-Up A-P Coronal Posture Pictures

Figure 2A-C. Post-R/C/Pre-ScoliBrace® TLSO, In-ScoliBrace® TLSO, and 1-Year Follow-Up P-A Coronal Posture Pictures

Figure 3A-C. Post-R/C/Pre-ScoliBrace® TLSO, Post-ScoliBrace® TLSO/CBP® Treatment, and 1-Year Follow-Up P-A Full Spine Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal vertical axis. The red lines represent coronal translation of landmark vertebrae (T1 and T12) from the coronal vertical axis through S1. The yellow lines represent the Cobb T10-L4 (apex at T12) angle of the patient.

Figure 4. Post-R-C/Pre-ScoliBrace® TLSO Modified Ferguson Radiograph

Image Features: The green lines represent the vertical axes through the hip and true horizontal lines. The red lines represent the sacral base line with respect to a true horizontal and femur heads line with respect to a true horizontal.

Figure 5A-B. Seated and Standing Mirror Image® Posturing for MI Adjustments Using Impulse® Adjusting Instrument

Figure 6. Mirror Image® Exercises Using a Thoracic ScoliRoll®

Figure 7. Mirror Image® Traction Using a 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System

3

Improvement in Neck Pain, Low Back Pain, and Physical, Mental, and Behavioral Performance in a 15-Year-Old Female Diagnosed With Attention Deficit Disorder and Depression Following Correction of Adolescent Idiopathic Scoliotic Spinal Alignment and Posture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Corrective Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report and 6-Month Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case demonstrating improvement in neck pain (NP), low back pain (LBP), and physical, mental, and behavioral performance in a 15-year-old female diagnosed with attention deficit disorder (ADD) and depression following correction of adolescent idiopathic scoliosis (AIS) spinal alignment and posture using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) corrective spinal rehabilitation with a 6-month follow-up.

Clinical Features: A 15-year-old female with NP, LBP, ADD, depression, and suspected AIS due to postural deformity was referred to a CBP® office from her traditional chiropractor. The patient received traditional conservative management (Diversified spinal manipulation) from early childhood, but it was unsuccessful in addressing the patient's spinal pain and postural deformity.

The patient's history revealed progressive worsening of NP, LBP, and increased anxiety surrounding her posture appearance, particularly when in a bathing suit or form fitting clothing. The patient states that she was prescribed medication to address the depression and ADD, but she felt it made her feel worse. The patient's parents expressed concern with the visible progression of the postural distortion and spinal pain. The pain had worsened over time and now affected the patient's activities of daily living (ADL) including sitting in school and standing at work.

Pre-treatment physical examination revealed asymmetry and reduction during cervical right (28°) and left (34°) lateral flexion (normal is 45°) and lumbar right (26°) and left (17°) lateral flexion (normal is 30°) using a Commander Echo Digital Inclinometer (JTECH Medical, Midvale, UT, USA). Motion and static palpation revealed spinal restriction in the cervical, thoracic, and lumbar regions. Postural asymmetry and trunk rotation was noted during Adams forward bending test. The patient presented with no positive neurological findings.

Pre-treatment posture analysis was performed using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA). Coronal posture analysis showed the patient had right pelvic (-TxP), thorax (-TxT), and head (-TxH) translation and left head lateral flexion (-RzH) (Figure 1A). Sagittal posture analysis showed posterior pelvic (-TzP), thorax (-TzT) and anterior head (+TzH) translation with cervical flexion (+RxH) (Figure 2A). Total coronal postural deviations measured 12.5 cm and total sagittal postural deviations measured 9.9 cm.

Pre-treatment anterior-to-posterior (AP) lumbar radiographic examination and analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records (EHR) Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA) and revealed a left AIS with a lateral curvature Cobb angle from T9 to L2 with a T12 apex (Cobb T9-L2 (T12)) measuring 33.1° (ideal is 0°) and coronal translation of T12 (apex) with respect to S1 (Tx T12-S1) measuring 55.7 mm (Figure 3A).

The patient completed a Short-Form 36 (SF-36) health-related quality of life (HRQOL) questionnaire to assess self-reported effects of the patient's scoliosis, NP, and LBP on her HRQOL. The SF-36 provides scaled scores for nine different HRQOL domains on a scale of 0 to 100, where 0 is the lowest HRQOL and 100 is the highest. Pre-treatment scores showed:

Physical Functioning (PF) was 95, Role Limitations due to Physical (RLP) was 75, Role Limitations due to Emotional (RLE) was 100, Energy (E) was 35, Emotional Well-Being (EWB) was 68, Social Function (SF) was 75, Pain (P) was 45.5, General Health (GH) was 65 and Change in Health Status (Δ HS) was 25.

Intervention & Outcomes: The patient was treated 22 times in-office over 2 months. The patient received Diversified spinal manipulation and CBP[®] Mirror Image[®] (MI) adjustments using a drop table and Impulse[®] Adjusting Instrument (Neuromechanical Innovations, Chandler, AZ, USA). MI drop table adjustments involved positioning the patient prone and -TxT and -TxH on a chiropractic drop table while applying the Impulse[®] Adjusting Instrument or manual drop table adjustments to the pelvis and cervical spine. Prior to each adjustment, the patient performed spinopelvic and core strengthening exercises seated on an air-inflated balance cushion for 30 to 60 seconds.

MI mechanical traction was performed on a 3-D Denneroll[™] Traction Table System (Denneroll[™] Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) with the patient left side down (LSD) on a Thoracic ScoliRoll[®] Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll[™] Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) positioned between T10-T12 and straps pulling down leveraging against the ScoliRoll at the patient's trochanters and at T6-T8 (Figure 4). MI mechanical traction started at 5 minutes and gradually increased to a maximum of 20 minutes each visit.

At-home MI therapeutic exercises and mechanical traction was prescribed. At-home MI exercises consisted of -TxT followed by -RzT (confirmed by x-ray based on the non-commutative property of finite rotational angles under addition) (Figure 5A-B). At-home MI mechanical traction consisted of the patient positioned LSD on a Thoracic ScoliRoll[®] at T10-T12 for 20 minutes each day.

Two-month post-treatment radiographic examination revealed improvement in Cobb T9-L2 to 20.6° and Tx T12-S1 to 24.0 mm (Figure 3B). The patient and her parents reported that she experiencing physical and emotional improvements including decreased anxiety and depression and increased focus at school and work. The patient's parents stated that she had discontinued any anti-anxiety, depression medication. Going forward with treatment, the patient was prescribed weekly in-office Diversified and CBP[®] MI instrument adjusting and at-home MI therapeutic exercises and mechanical traction.

Four-month post-treatment posture analysis showed improvements in coronal and sagittal posture (Figure 2B). Total coronal postural deviations improved to 2.3 cm and total sagittal postural deviations to 1.0 cm. Four-month post-treatment radiographic analysis showed maintained improvement in Cobb T9-L2 and further improvement in Tx T12-S1 to 20.0 mm (Figure 3C). The patient was prescribed in-office Diversified and CBP[®] MI instrument adjusting every 2 weeks and to continue with her at-home MI exercise and traction.

Six-month follow-up radiographic analysis revealed regression of Cobb T9-L2 to 26.0° and Tx T12-S1 to 31.0 mm (Figure 3D). During the six months, the patient had been inconsistent with her in-office adjustments reported that she had discontinued her at-home care. Follow-up SF-36 showed HRQOL improvements in: RLP to 100, EWB to 72, SF to 100, P to 57, and Δ HS to 75. Follow-up digital inclinometry showed improvement in symmetry and ROM during cervical right (39°) and left (39°).

Conclusion: In this case, CBP[®] MI corrective chiropractic adjustments, therapeutic exercises, and mechanical traction were effective in correcting AIS with observed improvement in NP, LBP, and physical, mental, and behavioral performance in a 15-year-old female with ADD, depression, and AIS. More research is needed on this topic, specifically with correction of spinal alignment and posture in pediatric populations with AIS. It is worth noting that abnormal spinal alignment and posture during adolescence can be progressive and requires regular, ongoing monitoring and management. The "watch and wait" approach is not an effective strategy for safe and effective management of AIS.

Figure 1A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment Coronal Posture

Figure 2A-B. Pre- and Post-Treatment Sagittal Posture

Image Features: The green line represents a normal coronal posture. The red lines represent the actual coronal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks to analyze the patient's posture and the yellow dotted lines show the leg postural alignment.

Image Features: The green line represents a normal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 3A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment and 3-Month Follow-Up Lateral Full-Spine (Stitched Sectionals) Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal lumbar alignment. The red horizontal lines represent coronal translation of apex vertebra (T12) from vertical axis through S1. The yellow lines represent the Cobb T10-L2 angle.

Figure 4. Stress Radiographs: A) –TxT then –RzT, and B) –RzT then -TxT

Figure 5. Mirror Image® Traction Using a Thoracic ScoliRoll

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal lumbar alignment. The red lines represent the coronal lumbar alignment of the patient. The yellow lines represent the Cobb T10-L2 angle.

4

Improvement in Neck and Temporomandibular Pain, Dysfunction, and Disability and Health-Related Quality-of-Life in a 34-Year-Old Female Following Reduction of Mid-Cervical Kyphosis Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Spinal Rehabilitation: A Case Report with 14-Month Follow-Up.

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case showing the improvement of health-related quality-of-life (HRQOL) following the improvement of mid-cervical kyphosis using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) corrective chiropractic care methods with a 14-month follow-up.

Clinic Features: A 34-year-old female presented to a chiropractic office with complaints of a constant grinding feeling at base of neck, neck discomfort rated 7/10 on a numeric rating scale (NRS) (0-10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is maximum pain), neck and shoulder muscle tightness, weakness in the neck, low back pain (LBP) rated 2/10, and right temporomandibular joint (TMJ) pain. The patient also expressed concern for her posture and for the lack of flexibility in her neck. The patient reported that she was a passenger in a side impact motor vehicle collision (MVC) nine years prior (2012) that resulted in chronic neck pain (NP). The patient did not pursue any treatment after the 2012 MVC. The patient reported that she was driver in a rear end MVC seven years prior (2014) which resulted in intense NP and headaches. The patient did get treatment following the 2014 MVC over the course of seven months, which included physiotherapy (PT), massage therapy (MT), traditional chiropractic adjustments, acupuncture, and occasional use of ibuprofen (prescribed by her medical doctor). The patient reported she stopped traditional chiropractic adjustments at that time after she felt it was causing grinding in her neck. The patient reported that during the next seven years she continued to get regular neck pain flare ups, weakness in her neck, and that her neck was easily aggravated. She continued to get treatment as needed during this time, which included acupuncture, PT, chiropractic adjustments, and MT. The patient reported that she didn't feel like her neck was improving with the ongoing treatment she was receiving.

Pre-treatment patient reported outcomes (PRO) included the Neck Disability Index (NDI) to assess the patient's self-reported NP and disability scoring 6/50 (12%) indicating mild disability due to NP, a Revised Oswestry Disability Index (RODI) to assess the patient's self-reported LBP and related disability scoring a 6/50 (12%) indicating mild disability due to LBP, and a RAND 36 questionnaire to assess the patient's self-reported measure of HRQOL. The RAND 36 measures eight health domains on a scale of 0 to 100, where 0 is the lowest score and 100 is the highest score. The patient's pre-treatment RAND 36 scores before treatment were: physical functioning (PF) at 80, role limitation due to physical health problems (RP) at 0, role limitation due to emotional health problems (RE) at 67, energy/fatigue (EF) at 45, emotional well-being (EWB) at 48, social functioning (SF) at 75, pain (P) at 78, and general health (GH) at 60.

A pre-treatment physical examination was performed. Cervical range of motion (ROM) was full in all ranges except for right rotation, which was 75% of normal. There was pain reported with cervical flexion. Low back ROM was full in all ranges with no pain reported. Grip strength was measured using a CAMRY Electronic Hand Dynamometer (Model: EH101, Zhongshan Camry Electronic Co., Ltd., Guangdong, China) where an average of three grip strength measurements was taken for each hand. The patient was left hand dominant. Pre-treatment mean grip strength measured 41.0 pounds on the right and 41.0 pounds on the left. There was mild tenderness in the cervical paraspinal muscles upon palpation.

Pre-treatment posture analysis was evaluated using PostureScreen® Mobile Posture Analysis (PostureCo®, Inc.,

Trinity, FL, USA) and revealed the following: anterior head translation (+TzH), posterior thorax translation (-TzT), anterior pelvis translation (+TzP), and left upper thorax translation (+TxT) (Figures 1A & 2A). Pre-treatment neutral lateral cervical (NLC) and anterior-to-posterior lower cervical (APLC) radiographic analysis was performed using PostureRay® X-Ray Electronic Health Records Software (PostureCo, Inc., Trinity, FL, USA) and revealed the following: a decreased sagittal curvature (absolute rotational angle) of the cervical spine from C2 to C7 (ARA C2-C7) measuring -1.0° (ideal is -42°); a mid-cervical kyphosis from C3-C6 (ARA C3-C6) measuring 20.1° (ideal is -24.0°); translation of C2 with respect to C7 (Tz C2-C7) measuring 14.8 mm (ideal is 0 mm); and translation of C2 with respect to T7 (Tx C2-T7) measuring 10.2 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figures 3A & 4A).

Interventions & Outcomes: The patient was treated 34 times in-office over 3 months. The patient received Thompson drop table adjustments and CBP® Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments involving positioning the patient prone with cervical spine placed in extension, contact at C5, and using the drop piece (Figure 5A) and an Impulse® Adjusting Instrument (Neuromechanical Innovations, Chandler, AZ, USA) (Figure 5B) as well as with the patient lying supine with the cervical spine in extension with C5 on an L-SPA Cervical Adjusting Device (Lope Sagittal Plane Adjusting, Jayco Chiropractic Supply) (Figure 5C). Coronal MI adjustments involved using the Impulse® adjusting instrument with the patient standing in an overcorrected spinal alignment and posture including -TxT, -Tx C2-T7, and +TzT. MI exercises included cervical ROM exercises, stretches, post-isometric relaxation stretches, the use of a CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser (Chiropractic BioPhysics®, Eagle, ID, USA) (Figure 6), and combining -TxT, -Tx C2-T7, and +TzT. MI mechanical traction included 2-way cervical extension traction using Universal Tractioning Systems (UTS) Total Spine Unit (Universal Tractioning Systems, Inc., Las Vegas, NV, USA) with the patient in a seated position, posterior-to-anterior (PA) dynamic weighted pull at the mid-cervical spine, and a posterior static distraction pull to hold the head and neck in extension (Figure 7). The patient was prescribed at-home daily MI exercises using a CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser and daily MI traction using a medium Cervical Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) placed at the lower cervical spine.

Post-treatment posture analysis at three months showed improved posture in the sagittal and coronal plane (Figures 1B & 2B). Post-treatment radiographic examination and analysis revealed the following improvements in ARA C2-C7 to -20.0° , ARA C3-C6 to -2.4° , and Tx C2-T7 to -1.7 mm. Tz C2-C7 remained consistent measuring 14.6 mm (Figures 3B & 4B).

The patient reported improvement in neck pain to 2/10. At three months post-treatment, the patient reported a 50% reduction of grinding feeling in her neck, 50% reduction of right TMJ pain, and LBP occurring only with bending movements. There was improved cervical ROM, full in all ranges with pain in extension. There was no change in grip strength. There was mild tenderness in cervical paraspinal muscles. Post-treatment NDI improved to 2/50 indicating minimal or resolved disability; RODI score was consistent at 6/50, and there was improvement in the RAND 36 health domains PF to 95, RP to 75, RE to 100, and EWB to 92.

The patient continued with in-office maintenance care which consisted of 13 visits at once per month over 14 months. In-office treatment included Thompson drop table adjustments and CBP® MI adjustments. The patient reported continuing with home traction using the medium Cervical Denneroll™ two to three times per week.

14-month follow-up posture analysis showed maintained correction in coronal posture and continued improvement in TzH and TzP (Figures 1C & 2C). Follow-up radiographic examination and analysis revealed a maintained correction of ARA C2-C7 at -17.30 and improvement in Tz C2-C7 to 12.0 mm with overall improvements from pre-treatment measures (Figures 3C & 4C).

At 14-month follow-up, the patient reported an overall 50% improvement in neck grinding feeling, an overall improvement in neck discomfort (2/10), and an overall improvement in low back pain (2/10). Cervical ROM was full, maintained, and free of pain. Low back ROM was full, maintained, and free of pain. Grip strength remained unchanged. There was no tenderness in cervical paraspinal muscles upon palpation.

At 14-month follow-up, NDI score maintained at 2/50 and RODI score improved to 2/50. RAND 36 saw improvements in PF to 100 and EF to 65 and an overall improvement in the PF, RP, RE, EF, EWB, and GH domains and maintenance of the SF and P health domains from pre-treatment.

Conclusion: This case shows CBP® corrective MI exercises, adjustments, and traction are an effective method to correct a sagittal buckling of the cervical spine in a patient with past whiplash trauma related to multiple MVCs. Improvement in spinal alignment and posture may result in improvement and long-term maintenance of HRQOL. More high-quality research with long-term follow-up is needed to investigate the long-term effects of correction of spinal alignment and posture on HRWOL in a chronic NP population following MVC trauma.

Figure 1A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 6-Month Follow-Up Sagittal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal posture. The red lines represent the actual sagittal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 2A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 14-Month Follow-Up Coronal Posture Analysis

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal posture. The red lines represent the actual coronal posture of the patient. The yellow circles with the black ring inside are anatomical landmarks made to analyze the patient's posture.

Figure 3A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 14-Month Follow-Up Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal cervical spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual C2-C7 posterior tangent lines of the patient.

Figure 4A-C. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and 14-Month Follow-Up Neutral Lateral Cervical Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal coronal cervical spinal alignment. The red line represents the actual C2-T7 coronal spinal alignment of the patient.

Figure 3. CBP® Mirror Image® Adjustments: A) Drop Table, B) Impulse® Adjusting Instrument, and C) L-SPA

Figure 6. CBP® Mirror Image® Exercises with CBP® Pro-Lordotic Neck Exerciser

Figure 7. CBP® Mirror Image® Traction with Universal Tractioning Systems Total Spine Unit

5

Improvement of Severe, Chronic Mid-Back Pain and Disability Following Correction of Sagittal Spinal Alignment and Posture Using Chiropractic BioPhysics® Mirror Image® Spinal Rehabilitation Program: A Case Report with 9-Month Long-Term Follow-Up

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Abstract

Objective: To present a case showing an improvement in severe, chronic mid-back pain (MBP) and disability following sagittal correction of the thoracic spine using Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) Mirror Image® (MI) spinal rehabilitation with a nine-month long-term follow-up exam.

Clinical Features: A 40-year-old female was referred for corrective chiropractic care by her physical therapist (PT) for severe, chronic MBP that had not improved despite several months of PT, traditional chiropractic adjustments, and pain management trigger point injections. The patient reported a history of constant, severe, chronic MBP for over 10 years that worsened with time. She rated her pain as 8/10 at its worst and 6/10 on average on a numeric rating scale (NRS) of 0-10 where 0 is no pain and 10 is max pain. She reported that the pain had caused her to cease certain activities of daily living (ADL) and extended activities, such as Krav Maga.

Posture analysis revealed increased thoracic flexion (hyperkyphosis). Lateral thoracic radiographic examination showed a wedged vertebra at T6, an absolute rotational angle from T3 to T10 (ARA T3-T10) measuring 66.2° (ideal is 44°), and sagittal translation (in the z-axis) from T3 to T10 (Tz T3-T10) measuring -16.3 mm (ideal is 0 mm) (Figure 1A).

Intervention and Outcome: The patient was treated 37 times in-office over 3 months. The patient received Diversified spinal manipulation and Chiropractic BioPhysics® (CBP®) Mirror Image® (MI) adjustments using a chiropractic drop table and instrument adjusting using an Erchonia® Adjustor™ instrument (Erchonia Corporation, Fountain Inn, SC, USA) (Figure 2A-B). The MI therapies involve positioning the patient in a corrected or over-corrected postural position. In the supine position, the patient had a 3.5" foam block placed under the thorax with the pelvis flat on the bench (Figure 2A). In the prone position, the patient had a 3.5" foam block placed under her anterior superior iliac spines (ASIS) with the thorax translated anteriorly (+TzT) and extended (-RxT) to reduce posterior thorax translation and thoracic flexion (Figure 2B). Sagittal MI mechanical traction was performed in a supine position using the 3-D Denneroll™ Traction Table System (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) with a Thoracic Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotic (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) placed at the apex of the thoracic hyperkyphosis inducing +TzT and -RxT. As the patient's tolerance increased, a posterior weighted pull (7 lbs.) of the head was applied to increase thoracic extension (Figure 2C). The patient was able to tolerate 20 minutes of MI traction by the third week of care. MI therapeutic exercises included supine thoracic foam rolling exercises on the floor.

A post-treatment exam was performed following 37 CBP® MI spinal rehabilitation visits over 3 months. The patient stated that her MBP was now occasional and mild and she rated her pain as 4/10 at its worst and 2/10 on average. She stated she resumed all ADLs including exercise, usually with no pain at all. Post-treatment posture analysis revealed improvement in sagittal thoracic posture. Post-treatment lateral thoracic radiographic examination showed improvement in ARA T3-T10 to 45.2°, however Tz T3-T10 moved posterior to -31.6 mm (Figure 1B). The patient was aware that the

wedged shape of her T6 vertebrae would lend itself to regression of her thoracic hyperkyphosis, and she understands the need for ongoing supportive therapy. At-home therapies were prescribed for the patient including MI mechanical traction using the Denneroll™ Posture Regainer Compression Extension System Unit (Denneroll™ Spinal Orthotics, New South Wales, Australia) and therapeutic exercise that recreated the in-office therapies. The patient continued supportive in-office treatments at an average of one day per week and she reported performing home traction 3-4 days per week for 2 months after which she reduced at-home MI mechanical traction frequency to an average of one day per week.

A long-term follow-up exam was performed following nine months and the patient stated that her MBP had maintained as occasional and mild. She stated she was able to continue all ADLs including exercise, usually with no pain at all. Long-term follow-up posture analysis revealed maintained improvement in sagittal thoracic posture. Long-term follow-up lateral thoracic radiographic examination showed sustained improvement in ARA T3-T10 to 47.7° and improvement in Tz T3-T10 to -11.2 mm (Figure 1C).

Conclusion: CBP® corrective chiropractic spinal rehabilitation was able to correct thoracic hyperkyphosis by approximately 20° in a 40-year-old female with a wedged T6 vertebra. Following thoracic spine correction, the patient reported improvement in constant, chronic MBP, disability, and ADL function. This success came after other unsuccessful previous interventions (PT, traditional chiropractic, and trigger point Injections). Improvement in sagittal spinal alignment and posture may result in long-term improvement in MBP, disability, and ADL function. This case study shows the need for more research involving spinal rehabilitation of thoracic hyperkyphosis and concomitant health outcome measures.

Figure 1. Pre-Treatment, Post-Treatment, and Long-Term Follow-Up Lateral Thoracic Spine Radiographs

Image Features: The green line represents a normal, ideal sagittal thoracic spinal alignment and posture. The red lines represent the actual T3-T10 posterior tangents.

Figure 2. CBP® Mirror Image® Corrective A) Supine Adjustment, B) Prone Adjustment, and C) Mechanical Traction Setups

